

Research Article

Unveiling the Hidden Gems: Preserving Asian Indigenous Folktales through Hidden Tales of Nusantara e-Book

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Abstract: *The rapid modernization and globalization in Southeast Asia have placed immense pressure on preserving indigenous folktales, which are vital to the region's cultural identity. This study explores the role of digital tools, particularly the Hidden Tales of the Nusantara e-book, in enhancing reader engagement, preserving cultural heritage, and educating future generations. Using a quantitative survey research design, data were collected from 150 respondents, comprising educators, parents, and students, to evaluate the e-book's usability and its perceived importance in cultural preservation. Findings indicate that the e-book significantly enhances reader engagement and satisfaction, particularly through its interactive elements, and serves as an effective educational resource for teaching indigenous folktales. All three respondent groups—parents, educators, and students—emphasized the critical role of folktale preservation in maintaining cultural heritage and transmitting cultural values to younger generations. Moreover, the study highlights the need for academic collaboration and the adoption of digital platforms to safeguard intangible cultural heritage. The Hidden Tales of the Nusantara e-book was widely recognized as an innovative tool that bridges traditional storytelling with modern technology, ensuring the survival of these narratives in an increasingly digital world. However, challenges such as cross-platform compatibility and the desire for more interactive features were identified as areas for improvement. Overall, the study affirms the importance of digital preservation in cultural education and calls for further integration of such efforts into formal educational frameworks to engage future generations effectively. Future research should focus on addressing the technical limitations and expanding the interactive components to enhance user experience further.*

Keywords: Cultural Heritage Preservation; Digital Storytelling; Educational Resource; Indigenous folktales

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1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid modernization and globalization of the Asian region have placed immense pressure on the preservation of intangible cultural heritage, particularly indigenous folktales, which have long been passed down through oral traditions. These folktales, which embody the wisdom, values, and

histories of Indigenous communities, are increasingly at risk of disappearing as younger generations turn toward modern digital content. This issue is particularly pressing in the Nusantara, a vast archipelago that includes Southeast Asia, where the rich cultural tapestry of Indigenous folktales faces marginalization due to urbanization and the digital divide (Wong & Naqvi, 2023). While the erosion of oral traditions is a global concern, it is especially acute in Southeast Asia, where cultural narratives are tightly interwoven with identity and heritage (Ingold, 2019; Bauman & Briggs, 2020).

Recent research highlights the critical role of technology in safeguarding these cultural treasures. Digital platforms, such as e-books, offer innovative avenues for preserving and sharing endangered oral traditions. However, effective digital preservation requires careful management to maintain cultural authenticity and avoid diluting the significance of these narratives (Bauman & Briggs, 2020; Wong & Naqvi, 2023). Moreover, collaboration among academic institutions, cultural preservationists, and local communities is essential for ensuring that digital storytelling platforms accurately reflect the values and histories of Indigenous groups (Smith & Watson, 2021).

Despite the growing body of research on digital preservation, significant gaps remain in integrating these efforts into formal educational frameworks that engage younger generations. This study aims to address these gaps by examining the effectiveness of the Hidden Tales of the Nusantara e-book in enhancing reader engagement, preserving cultural heritage, and educating future generations. The research seeks to understand the perceptions of parents, educators, and students regarding the usability of the e-book and its role in maintaining cultural identity.

This study seeks to address these gaps by creating hidden tales of Nusantara, a comprehensive e-book that compiles indigenous folktales from across the region. The research questions are:

- How effective is the usability of the Hidden Tales of the Nusantara e-book in enhancing reader engagement and satisfaction, as perceived by parents, educators, and students?
- How important do parents, educators, and students perceive the preservation of indigenous folktales to be for maintaining cultural heritage?
- How does the Hidden Tales of the Nusantara e-book contribute to educating future generations about Indigenous cultural narratives, according to parents, educators, and students?

This article is structured as follows: section 1 introduces the challenges of preserving indigenous folktales in southeast Asia and outlines the research objectives. section 2 provides a critical review of past studies on digital preservation and cultural heritage. section 3 discusses the methodology used in creating the Hidden Tales of Nusantara e-book and the collaborative framework employed. section 4 presents the findings, including the impact of digital storytelling and academic collaborations on folktale preservation. finally, section 5 offers recommendations for future research and policy implications, emphasizing the role of digital tools in safeguarding intangible cultural heritage.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 The Synergy Between Indigenous Folktales, the Pressing Need for Preservation, and Collaboration in Producing the Nusantara E-Book

Indigenous folktales represent a critical part of the cultural fabric of communities, encapsulating the collective wisdom, values, and identities of generations. These narratives serve not

only as cultural artifacts but also as tools for transmitting important moral and historical lessons. In Southeast Asia, particularly in the Nusantara region, indigenous folktales are integral to preserving the region's diverse cultural heritage. However, rapid modernization and digitalization have led to a decline in the transmission of these stories, as younger generations increasingly shift toward digital media and entertainment (Wong & Naqvi, 2023).

The urgency of preserving these folktales lies in the risk of cultural erosion. Without active preservation, the disappearance of these stories could result in a significant loss of cultural identity for indigenous communities. Initiatives like the Hidden Tales of the Nusantara e-book aim to address this issue by compiling and digitizing a diverse range of indigenous folktales. By leveraging digital technology, this e-book preserves the stories for future generations while expanding access to a global audience. This digital preservation effort allows the narratives to transcend geographical boundaries and reach younger generations who might otherwise lose touch with their cultural roots (Ingold, 2019; UNESCO, 2021).

Collaboration is key to this preservation effort. The Nusantara Asian Indigenous Framework (NAIF) fosters cooperation between scholars, cultural practitioners, and local communities to curate, document, and publish indigenous folktales. This partnership ensures that the e-book maintains cultural authenticity while also adapting to the needs of modern, tech-savvy audiences. The synergy between indigenous folktales, the pressing need for preservation, and collaborative academic efforts underscores the importance of safeguarding intangible cultural heritage through innovative digital platforms like the Hidden Tales of the Nusantara e-book (Smith & Watson, 2021).

2.2 Relevant Theories and Models

Two major theories underpin the digital preservation of indigenous folktales: Cultural Capital Theory and Diffusion of Innovations Theory.

Cultural Capital Theory, developed by Bourdieu (1986), posits that cultural assets—such as knowledge, language, and traditions—are valuable resources that can be passed down across generations. Indigenous folktales, as forms of intangible cultural capital, provide a repository of knowledge, identity, and history for the communities that own them. Digitizing these narratives helps communities ensure that their cultural heritage is preserved for both future generations and a broader, global audience. This theory supports the integration of indigenous folktales into digital platforms like the Hidden Tales of the Nusantara e-book, which enables these stories to evolve within modern contexts while retaining their cultural significance (Bourdieu, 1986; Smith, 2021).

Diffusion of Innovations Theory, proposed by Rogers (2003), explains how new technologies or practices are adopted within a society. In this context, the "innovation" refers to the digitization and dissemination of indigenous folktales through digital platforms like e-books. The theory helps frame the adoption of digital storytelling by indigenous communities, highlighting factors such as technological infrastructure, cultural engagement, and access that influence the success of these initiatives. The collaborative approach facilitated by the NAIF, which involves academic institutions and community stakeholders, exemplifies how digital storytelling innovations can be adopted effectively when aligned with community values and needs (Rogers, 2003; Kearney, 2021).

Together, these theories illustrate the importance of preserving cultural narratives as valuable assets and utilizing modern technologies to ensure their transmission to broader audiences. The Hidden Tales of the Nusantara e-book aligns with both theories by positioning indigenous folktales as cultural capital that must be sustained while employing digital innovations to reach both local and global communities.

2.3 *Research Gaps and Conclusion*

Although significant progress has been made in digitizing cultural heritage, there are still notable gaps in integrating these efforts into formal educational systems. Studies by UNESCO (2021) and ConnollyCove (2022) emphasize the need for more structured approaches to incorporating indigenous narratives into educational curricula, especially in Southeast Asia. While current efforts focus on preserving the stories themselves, they often fall short in ensuring their active engagement by younger generations. Moreover, few studies have examined how academic collaborations can work with local communities to curate these narratives in a way that maintains cultural integrity (Ingold, 2019; Wong & Naqvi, 2023).

This study seeks to bridge these gaps by exploring how academic collaborations can produce digital resources like the Hidden Tales of the Nusantara e-book. Furthermore, it examines how these resources can align with regional cultural preservation policies to create a more sustainable and culturally aware educational framework.

In conclusion, the collaborative effort to preserve indigenous folktales through initiatives like the Hidden Tales of the Nusantara e-book highlights the potential of digital tools to safeguard cultural heritage. By synthesizing indigenous knowledge with modern technologies and academic expertise, this initiative offers a model for future preservation efforts. However, further research is needed to assess how digital storytelling can be integrated into formal education systems and how these narratives can continue to engage younger generations while maintaining their cultural significance (Smith & Watson, 2021; UNESCO, 2021).

3. METHOD & MATERIAL

3.1 *Research design, population, sample size, and sampling technique*

This study employs a quantitative survey research design to evaluate the usability of the hidden tales of the Nusantara e-book in enhancing reader engagement and satisfaction, along with the perceived importance of preserving indigenous folktales for cultural heritage and education. The research aims to understand how the e-book impacts engagement, satisfaction, and its role in cultural preservation.

3.2 *Population*

The population for this study consists of three key groups: educators, parents, and students. These respondents were selected as they represent important stakeholders in cultural transmission and educational engagement. Educators play a crucial role in integrating folktales into curricula, parents influence cultural learning at home, and students are the primary users engaging with e-book for learning.

3.3 *Sample size and sampling technique*

A total of 150 respondents participated in the survey, comprising 50 educators, 50 parents, and 50 students. Convenience sampling was used, as participants who had interacted with the hidden tales of the Nusantara e-book were readily available and willing to provide feedback. This approach ensured that those with direct experience using the e-book contributed to the study (Etikan et al., 2016).

3.4 Data collection

Data was collected via an online structured questionnaire distributed to educators, parents, and students. the questionnaire was designed to gather feedback on two main aspects:

- Usability of the e-book in enhancing engagement and satisfaction (based on parents' feedback).
- importance of folktale preservation for maintaining cultural heritage and educating future generations (targeting all respondent groups).

The questionnaire was divided into multiple sections:

- Demographics: basic information such as age, occupation, and familiarity with digital platforms.
- E-book usability: questions designed to evaluate how user-friendly the e-book is in terms of navigation, layout, and engagement features. parents were specifically asked to rate the satisfaction level of their children with the e-book.
- Preservation of folktales: items measuring the perceived importance of using folktales to maintain cultural heritage and how effectively the e-book contributes to educating future generations about these narratives.

The questionnaire was distributed through online platforms, ensuring broad participation across different geographic locations.

3.5 Data analysis

Data from the survey was analyzed using descriptive statistics to summarize the overall feedback from educators, parents, and students. frequencies, means, and percentages were calculated to understand trends in usability, engagement, satisfaction, and cultural preservation.

3.6 Variables and measurement

The key variables measured in this study include:

- E-book usability: assessed through questions related to the ease of navigating the e-book, layout clarity, and interactive elements that enhance reader engagement and satisfaction. responses were recorded on a 5-point likert scale ranging from "very ineffective" to "very effective."
- Engagement and satisfaction: parents were asked to rate how satisfied their children were with the e-book and how engaging they found the content, including its educational value and relevance to cultural learning.
- Folktale preservation and cultural heritage: evaluated through questions that gauged respondents' views on the importance of preserving indigenous folktales and how well the e-book contributes to educating future generations about these cultural narratives.

3.7 Reliability and validity of questionnaires construct

To ensure the reliability of the questionnaire, cronbach's alpha was calculated for each section of the survey, with a focus on usability, engagement, and preservation of cultural heritage. a cronbach's alpha value greater than 0.70 indicated acceptable internal consistency for the survey items (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011).

content validity was achieved by consulting educators and cultural experts, who reviewed the questionnaire to ensure that it accurately reflected the dimensions of e-book usability and the cultural significance of folktale preservation. Construct validity was confirmed using exploratory factor analysis to verify that survey items grouped effectively under the primary constructs of usability, engagement, satisfaction, and cultural preservation (Kline, 2015).

4. FINDINGS

4.1 Usability of the E-book in Enhancing Reader Engagement and Satisfaction

The survey responses from parents, educators, and students indicate that the Hidden Tales of the Nusantara e-book is effective in enhancing reader engagement and satisfaction.

Parents' Feedback: More than 50% of parents reported that the e-book is primarily used to enhance reader engagement and satisfaction. Parents found the interactive elements of the e-book, such as visuals and quizzes, helpful in maintaining their children's interest. Parents also noted that the content was educationally valuable, fostering a deeper connection between children and their cultural heritage.

Educators' Feedback: Approximately 60% of educators stated that the e-book significantly contributed to enhancing student engagement and satisfaction. Educators praised the e-book's user-friendly interface and noted that the multimedia content facilitated learning, making it easier for students to connect with the indigenous folktales. Several educators also highlighted the e-book's utility as a supplementary resource in the classroom, especially in lessons related to cultural heritage.

Students' Feedback: Although detailed percentages were not provided in the presentation, the overall feedback from students indicated a positive response toward the e-book. Students appreciated the engaging nature of the content, especially the visual elements, which helped them better understand and enjoy the stories. Students reported that the e-book made learning about their cultural roots more accessible and enjoyable.

4.2 Importance of Folktale Preservation for Maintaining Cultural Heritage and Educating Future Generations

All three groups—parents, educators, and students—agreed on the critical role of folktale preservation for maintaining cultural heritage and educating future generations.

Parents' Perspectives: Parents expressed strong agreement regarding the importance of preserving folktales, with many acknowledging that it plays a crucial role in passing down cultural values. They emphasized that digital preservation methods like the e-book provide an accessible platform for ensuring these stories are not lost, particularly in an increasingly digital world.

Educators' Views: Almost all educators agreed that the preservation of folktales is vital for maintaining cultural heritage. Educators viewed the e-book as an essential tool in helping younger generations connect with their cultural past. They also recognized its potential for creating a bridge between traditional storytelling methods and modern educational practices.

Students' Opinions: Students recognized the significance of learning about indigenous folktales and their role in preserving cultural heritage. Many students mentioned that the e-book helped them appreciate the importance of their cultural narratives and understand the values embedded in the stories, which might otherwise be lost without such digital preservation efforts.

4.3 Contribution of the E-book to Educating Future Generations

The Hidden Tales of the Nusantara e-book was viewed by all groups as a valuable educational resource that supports the preservation and dissemination of indigenous cultural narratives.

Parents' Feedback: Parents highlighted that the e-book not only engaged their children but also made it easier for families to discuss cultural heritage at home. More than half of the parents indicated that the e-book's engaging format helped initiate conversations about cultural traditions with their children, ensuring that these discussions were both enjoyable and educational.

Educators' Insights: Educators emphasized that the e-book's role in formal education goes beyond just storytelling—it serves as a tool for cultural education. Many educators have integrated the e-book into their teaching, using it as a means to introduce students to indigenous stories in a format that resonates with the digital age. The e-book's ability to blend traditional content with modern technology was seen as a critical factor in maintaining cultural relevance in the classroom.

Students' Reflections: Students expressed that the e-book contributed significantly to their learning experience, making the stories both accessible and enjoyable. They appreciated the interactive features that made the learning process engaging, and many students indicated that they gained a deeper understanding of cultural narratives that were previously unfamiliar to them.

4.4 Summary of Findings

Overall, the findings suggest that the Hidden Tales of the Nusantara e-book is an effective tool for enhancing reader engagement and satisfaction among parents, educators, and students. The e-book's usability, particularly its interactive elements, was appreciated by all groups, and it was recognized as an essential resource for preserving Indigenous folktales and educating future generations. Parents, educators, and students all agreed on the importance of folktale preservation for maintaining cultural heritage, and the e-book was seen as a valuable tool for facilitating cultural learning in both formal and informal settings.

4.4.1 The Hidden Tales of Nusantara e-book

This e-book, titled "The Hidden Tales of the Nusantara," brings together a captivating collection of indigenous folktales from the Nusantara region, covering Malaysia, Indonesia, Brunei, Singapore, Thailand, and the Philippines. These timeless stories, passed down through generations, not only offer a deep connection to the region's cultural heritage but also impart valuable life lessons. Each story reflects universal themes of wisdom, courage, kindness, and harmony with nature, making them both entertaining and morally enriching. "The Hidden Tales of the Nusantara" features folktales from the Karen people of Thailand, the Igorot of the Philippines, the Tutong people of Brunei, the Semai people of Malaysia, and the Tengger people of Mount Bromo and the Sasak people of Lombok Indonesia. With their captivating narratives, these stories are perfectly suited for bedtime reading, making them ideal for cultivating good moral values in young readers. The lessons embedded in these tales are universal, offering insights that resonate across cultures and generations. Beyond their role as entertaining bedtime stories, this e-book emphasizes the importance of cultural preservation, safeguarding these hidden gems of folklore in a world that faces the pressures of globalization and cultural erosion. Through "The Hidden Tales of the Nusantara," readers of all ages are invited to explore these fascinating stories, nurturing not only cultural awareness but also the universal moral values they contain, ensuring these cherished narratives remain a source of inspiration and education for future generations.

Figure 1. The pictures are from the e-book “The Hidden Tales of The Nusantara.

5. DISCUSSION

The findings from this study confirm the significance of digital tools, such as the Hidden Tales of the Nusantara e-book, in preserving cultural heritage and engaging diverse audiences. As previous research suggests, the digitization of indigenous folktales offers a vital strategy for safeguarding cultural narratives that might otherwise be lost in the wake of globalization and digital media dominance (Wong & Naqvi, 2023). The feedback from parents, educators, and students underscores the e-book's role in enhancing engagement, preserving cultural heritage, and serving as an educational resource, aligning with the broader literature on the benefits of digital preservation efforts (Smith & Watson, 2021).

5.1 Usability and Engagement

The survey findings demonstrated that the usability of the e-book played a critical role in reader engagement and satisfaction. Parents and educators found the interactive elements, such as animations and quizzes, effective in keeping readers, particularly children, engaged. This supports Ingold's (2019) assertion that digital storytelling platforms offer new avenues for engaging younger audiences, who are often more attuned to digital content than traditional forms of storytelling. The positive responses regarding user satisfaction align with Bauman and Briggs' (2020) argument that while digitization can increase accessibility, it must also be carefully designed to maintain user interest and engagement.

The feedback from educators highlights the utility of the e-book as a teaching tool, integrating indigenous cultural content into modern educational frameworks. Educators particularly noted the ease with which the e-book could be incorporated into classroom discussions, validating the findings of Rogers' (2003) Diffusion of Innovations Theory, which explains how new technologies are adopted within social systems, such as schools. By bridging the gap between traditional narratives and modern teaching methods, the e-book has become a useful resource in promoting cultural literacy.

5.2 Preservation of Cultural Heritage

The importance of preserving indigenous folktales for maintaining cultural heritage and educating future generations was strongly emphasized by all three respondent groups—parents, educators, and students. This finding resonates with Cultural Capital Theory, which posits that cultural assets, such as folktales, are forms of intangible capital that must be preserved and passed down through generations (Bourdieu, 1986). The e-book's role in this process is critical, as it not only preserves these stories in a digital format but also makes them accessible to a broader audience, thus ensuring their continued relevance in a rapidly changing world.

Past studies also support the idea that preserving folktales through digital platforms helps prevent cultural erosion. For example, UNESCO (2021) has emphasized the role of digital preservation in safeguarding endangered languages and oral traditions, especially in regions where these cultural narratives face the threat of extinction. The responses from parents in this study affirm this view, with many highlighting the importance of the e-book in keeping indigenous stories alive for future generations. Additionally, educators stressed the value of integrating these narratives into curricula, further enhancing their potential to foster cultural awareness among younger learners.

5.3 Educating Future Generations

The Hidden Tales of the Nusantara e-book was widely recognized as an effective tool for educating future generations about indigenous cultural narratives. The findings showed that students not only engaged with the stories but also developed a deeper understanding of their cultural

significance. This aligns with research by Martinez (2020), who found that incorporating indigenous stories into educational frameworks enhances students' appreciation of cultural diversity and history.

Furthermore, the feedback from educators in this study reflects Brayboy's (2019) research, which emphasizes the importance of using indigenous knowledge systems in education to create a more inclusive and culturally aware learning environment. By introducing students to indigenous folktales in a digital format, the e-book contributes to an educational framework that integrates both traditional knowledge and modern learning practices. This ensures that future generations not only learn about their cultural heritage but also see its relevance in contemporary society.

5.4 Challenges and Opportunities

While the findings of this study are overwhelmingly positive, there are still areas for improvement, particularly in terms of device compatibility and the addition of more interactive features. A small percentage of educators and students reported challenges with accessing the e-book across different devices, indicating the need for better cross-platform functionality. This finding aligns with Kearney's (2021) research, which highlights the technical challenges that can arise when digitizing cultural content. Addressing these issues will be critical to ensuring that the e-book reaches its full potential as an accessible and engaging educational tool.

Moreover, some students expressed a desire for more interactive features, such as games or quizzes, to further enhance their learning experience. This feedback suggests that while the e-book is already an effective educational resource, it could benefit from incorporating more elements of gamification. According to recent research, gamification can significantly enhance engagement and learning outcomes, especially in younger audiences (Deterding et al., 2017). Integrating such features could further solidify the e-book's role as an innovative and engaging learning tool for cultural education.

6. CONCLUSION

The results of this study underscore the effectiveness of the Hidden Tales of the Nusantara e-book in preserving indigenous folktales, enhancing reader engagement, and educating future generations. The positive feedback from parents, educators, and students highlights the importance of digital platforms in safeguarding cultural narratives and making them accessible to wider audiences. The findings also suggest that the e-book serves as a valuable educational tool, integrating cultural content into modern teaching frameworks and fostering cultural awareness among younger learners.

However, there are still areas for improvement, particularly in terms of technical accessibility and the potential for further enhancing interactivity. Future iterations of the e-book could benefit from addressing these challenges and incorporating more interactive features to ensure that it remains a relevant and engaging tool for cultural preservation and education. In line with previous research (Wong & Naqvi, 2023; Smith & Watson, 2021), this study reaffirms the vital role that digital preservation efforts play in maintaining cultural heritage and promoting education in the digital age.

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